

gene from DZ78, which carries *xa5* and *xa7*.

F₁ hybrids derived from crosses between 85-21416 and 16 japonica cultivars in 1989 were fertile, with 84.2 ± 2.8% average spikelet fertility. 85-21416 carries a

compatibility gene that appears allelic to *S-5ⁿ*. Fairly fertile hybrids were obtained from crosses between 85-21416 and cultivars known to have the wide-compatibility gene *S-5ⁿ* (Ketan Nangka, CPSL017, and 02428) (Table 2). The

compatibility gene carried by 85-21416 could have come from indica DZ78, which produced a compatible intersubspecific hybrid when crossed with japonica tester cultivar Akihikari (69.1 ± 1.1% spikelet fertility in 1992). ■

RFLP mapping of blast resistance gene *Pi-k^m* in rice

R. Kaji and T. Ogawa, Kyushu National Agricultural Experiment Station, Chikugo, Fukuoka 833, Japan

Blast resistance gene *Pi-k* is located on chromosome 11 (Goto et al 1981) and has multiple alleles *Pi-k^h*, *Pi-k^m*, and *Pi-k^p* (Kiyosawa 1978). Although restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) linkage analysis indicated that *Pi-k* is located on chromosome 11, no RFLP marker closely linked to *Pi-k* was found at that time. For fine-mapping of *Pi-k* loci, we conducted RFLP analysis of *Pi-k^m* and

RFLP markers using F₃ lines from the cross between Tohoku IL4 (japonica near-isogenic line with *Pi-k^m* introgressed from Tsuyuake) and CO 39 (susceptible indica variety).

Each F₃ line was inoculated with Japanese blast race 003 at 3-4 leaf stage using the spray method. The F₃ lines were classified either as resistant (or segregating) lines or susceptible lines 30 d after inoculation.

DNA was extracted from the leaves of each F₃ line using the cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide method. Total DNA was digested with restriction enzymes (*Eco*RI, *Hind*III, and *Dra*I) and blotted onto a positively charged nylon membrane filter using capillary transfer after electrophoresis. RFLP landmarks on chromosome 11 and

cDNA clone R1506 (provided by NIAR/STAFF) were used. Linkage analyses of *Pi-k^m* and the RFLP markers are shown in the table. Recombination values calculated using the maximum likelihood method were converted into genetic map distances (cM) using the Kosambi function. All RFLP markers used in this study were linked to *Pi-k^m*, notably L190, which was closely linked to *Pi-k^m* at about 1.5 cM.

Pi-k^m is located on chromosome 11 in the RFLP linkage map between L190 and R1506 (see figure). Because L190 is located on the terminal region of chromosome 11 (Nagamura et al 1993), results of our study correspond to those of a classical linkage map. For further fine-mapping of the *Pi-k^m* loci, we will subject more F₃ lines to RFLP analysis. ■

Linkage analysis among *Pi-k^m* and RFLP markers.

Gene pair		Segregation mode in F ₃										Genetic map distance (cM)
A	B	AABB	AABb	AAbb	AaBB	AaBb	Aabb	aaBB	aaBb	aabb		
<i>Pi-k^m</i>	L190	36	61	1				0	1	37	1.5 ± 1.2	
	R1506	29	47	3				0	2	32	4.3 ± 1.0	
	G181	28	62	5				0	7	34	8.4 ± 1.9	
	G1465	31	80	12				1	12	32	15.8 ± 2.4	
L190	R1506	26	5	1	1	31	2	0	1	27	6.0 ± 2.6	
	G181	26	3	1	0	42	5	0	6	29	7.4 ± 1.8	
	G1465	20	13	3	6	48	8	1	10	27	19.1 ± 3.0	
R1506	G181	23	3	0	3	37	3	0	6	27	7.7 ± 1.8	
	G1465	18	10	1	8	33	8	0	9	26	18.5 ± 1.9	
G181	G1465	19	8	1	6	54	9	0	8	31	13.3 ± 2.8	

Linkage map of *Pi-k^m* and RFLP markers on chromosome 11.

Indica/japonica doubled haploid population as a model for mapping rice yellow mottle virus and blast resistance genes

A. Ghesquiere, M. Lorieux, Institut Français de recherche scientifique développement en coopération (ORSTOM), BP 5045, 34032 Montpellier Cedex 1, France; E. Roumen, Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique par le développement (CIRAD), BP 5035, 34032 Montpellier Cedex 1, France; L. Albar, ORSTOM and CIRAD; D. Fargette, ORSTOM; N. Huang, IRRI; and J. L. Nottoghem, CIRAD

Rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) is the most damaging rice pest in irrigated fields of West Africa. Blast is a widespread disease causing severe yield losses. To map several resistance genes, we used two doubled haploid (DH) populations derived from the F₁ hybrids IR64/Azucena and IRAT 177/Apuraj and segregating for many agronomic traits. This analysis relied on core restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) maps developed at IRRI for the IR64/Azucena population (Huang et al 1994) and at Cornell University for the IRAT 177/Apuraj population (Yu et al 1991).

RYMV scoring. The resistance analysis involved 74 IR64/Azucena DH lines and 48 IRAT 177/Apuraj DH lines. Nineteen-day-old rice plants were mechanically inoculated with a RYMV isolate collected from Mali. Two weeks after inoculation, newly emerged leaves were harvested for assessment of virus concentration by serological methods involving ACP- or DAS-enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays.

Blast scoring. An initial survey involving the parents and 20 IR64/Azucena DH lines allowed us to select six diverse strains of *Magnaporthe grisea* apparently inter-

acting with different genes or quantitative trait loci (QTLs) in this population (Roumen et al, 1996, unpubl.data). The 135 mapped DH lines were evaluated for resistance to the six blast strains. Twenty to twenty-five plants from each DH line were grown in the glasshouse and inoculated with spore suspensions by spraying or injecting into sheaths of rice plants at the 4-5 leaf stage. Resistance scores ranged from 0 (complete resistance) to 6 (high susceptibility).

Genetic mapping. For chromosome 12, additional RFLP markers were mapped on the available 183 DH lines of IR64/Azucena progeny to refine QTL/major gene locations. Clones mapped on an inter-specific backcross were used as probes (Causse et al 1994), and RFLP was identified using a chemiluminescent kit following CIMMYT protocols (Hoisington et al 1994). In addition, we conducted bulked segregant analysis (BSA) as described by Michelmore et al (1991) to compare the RYMV susceptible/resistant pools with 300 randomly amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) primers. Interval mapping identified the loci involved in resistance to RYMV or blast (Lander and Botstein 1989) and confirmed by the Kruskal & Wallis nonparametric test using MapQTL 2.4.

RYMV resistance. For the IR64/Azucena population, interval mapping revealed only one locus associated with significant effects on RYMV resistance on chromosome 12 (LOD=2.57), close to the RG341 marker. This locus probably corresponds to a QTL with a relatively high percentage of explained trait variance ($R^2=0.30$). This localization was found highly consistent with that obtained by BSA. A 800-bp band amplified with Op O10 primer was also detected by BSA and mapped at 2.7 cM from RG341. A QTL was detected at the same location for IRAT 177/Apuraj population (LOD=3.27; $R^2=0.33$). Because the two recombinant populations shared the five RFLP markers on chromosome 12, an integrative map of chromosome 12 was established on 2.58 individuals, and the QTL was reinforced (LOD=5.57; $R^2=0.37$). This result clearly indicates that the resistance genes from IRAT 177 and Azucena were allelic or closely linked.

Blast resistance. Significant resistance loci observed in the IR64/Azucena DH population are summarized in the table. Some loci were strain-specific while others were common to different strains. For instance, a QTL on chromosome 2 was detected with strains Br26, Ch66, and Ch72. Other strains, such as Br26, could reveal up to four different QTLs. Differential QTLs for strain Ph68 were detected following inoculation by spray or injection. QTLs for blast resistance tend to cluster on rice chromosomes (McCouch et al 1994). Two QTLs or major genes are lying on the opposite sides of RG869 (chromosome 12) in the same pattern as observed by Yu et al (1991) and could correspond to *Pi4(t)* and *Pi6(t)* resistance genes. For CD69 strain,

the locus detected on chromosome 12 probably corresponds to a major gene because it explained about 90% of the trait variance. In addition, the results suggest that one or two other different QTLs could exist in the vicinity of RG457. Similarly, loci detected on other chromosomes could correspond to previously located genes (see table).

A cluster of resistance genes or QTLs involving a major QTL for resistance to RYMV and several blast resistance genes or alleles was observed on a relatively small portion of chromosome 12 (see figure). This chromosome segment will need special attention and further evaluation for determining its implications in breeding for resistance in rice.

Loci identified for resistance to 6 blast isolates by a QTL detection method (interval mapping) in IR64/Azucena cross.^a

Chromosome	Marker/interval	Map position (cM)	BI isolates ^b						Possible correspondence with known loci
			Br26 spr	Ph68 spr or inj	CD69 spr	Ch66 inj	Ch72 inj	C16 spr	
1	RG173	147.4						2.9	
	RG532	177.8						24.1 (a) ^c	
2	RG520	0	5.8			3.0	2.3		
			(20.5 (i) ^d)		11.6 (i)	9.5 (i)			
2	RZ123	16.6	5.7						
	RG654	27.4	18.8 (i)						
5	RG313	37.7		2.8 ^e					
				14.1 (a)					
				3.1					
	RZ225	152.5		15.2 (a)					
6	RG213	20.7				3.0			<i>Pi2 (t)</i> or <i>Pi9 (t)</i>
						13.8 (i)			
6	RZ144	33.4	1.9	1.5					
	RZ667	35.2	7.1 (i)	8.2 (i)					
8	G104	34.6					6.1		<i>Pi11 (t)</i>
	RZ617	41.6					22.2 (i)		
	RG667	92.8					2.3		
	RG451	111.1					8.9 (i)		
10	RZ500	0.0		2.2 ⁱ			2.2		
	CD093	25.0		8.0 (a)			10.2 (a)		
11	RG1094	100.2				4.8	4.2		<i>Pi-a?</i>
	RG118	111.8				21.6 (i)	20.2 (i)		
12	RG457 010	57.9		100.0 ⁱ					
		73.5		34.0 (i)					
12	010	73.5		10.8					<i>Pi4 (t)</i> = <i>Pi62?</i> = <i>Pi-ta?</i> <i>Pi6 (t)</i>
	RG341	76.4		37.0 (i)					
12	RG869	76.4	6.1		25.0				
	RZ816	103.2	23.2 (i)		90.0 (i)				

^aLoci with low significance (1.5 < LOD score < 2.3) are reported if detected with at least two isolates. Letters in regular font = LOD score; in italics = % of explained variance by the locus. ^bspr = inoculation by spray; inj = inoculation by injection. ^c(a) = resistance locus brought by Azucena. ^d(i) = resistance locus brought by IR64. ^e_i = locus detected with injection method only.

Alignment of QTLs/major genes for RYMV and blast resistance on rice chromosome 12. Loci were detected using DH lines derived from two indica/japonica F₁ hybrids (IR64/Azucena and IRAT 177/Apura). Vertical dashed line indicates position of RG869 marker, which separates *Pi4* and *Pi6* in other studies. The peaks observed on each side of the line could correspond to these two genes.

Cited references

Causse M, Fulton TM, Cho YG, Ahn SN, Chungwongse J, Wu K, Xiao J, Yu Z, Ronald PC, Harrington SE, Second G, MacCouch SR, Tanksley SD. 1994. Saturated molecular map of the rice genome based on an inter-specific backcross population. *Genetics* 138:1251-1274.

Hoisington D, Khairallah M, Gonzalez-de-Leon D. 1994. Laboratory protocols: CIMMYT Applied Molecular Genetics Laboratory. Second edition. Mexico D. F.: International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center.

Huang N, McCouch S, Mew T, Parco A, Guiderdoni E. 1994. Development of an RFLP map from a doubled haploid population rice. *Rice Genet. Newsl.* 11:134-137.

Lander ES, Botstein D. 1989. Mapping Mendelian factors underlying quantitative traits using RFLP linkage maps. *Genetics* 121:185-199.

McCouch SR, Nelson KJ, Tohme J, Leigler KS. 1993. Mapping of blast resistance genes in rice. In: Rice blast disease. RS Zeigler, SA Leong, PS Teng, editors. London: CABI and Manila: International Rice Research Institute. p 167-186.

Yu ZH. 1991. Molecular mapping of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) genes via linkage to restriction fragment polymorphism, (RFLP) markers. Ph D thesis, Cornell University, Ithaca, N.Y.

Yu ZH, Mackill DJ, Bonmann JM, Tanksley SD. 1991. Tagging genes for blast resistance via linkage to RFLP markers. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* 81:471-476. ■

Characterization of a pathogenesis-related gene family induced in rice infected with *Magnaporthe grisea*

J. D. McGee, Botany and Plant Pathology Department, Purdue University (PU), West Lafayette, IN 47907, USA; N. J. Talbot, T. Bhargava, and J. E. Hamer, Biology Department, PU; and T. K. Hodges, Botany and Plant Pathology Department, PU

Fungal pathogens, such as *Magnaporthe grisea* and *Rhizoctonia solani* can cause significant yield losses. Increased disease resistance can be obtained in plants transformed with genes encoding known antifungal proteins, such as the hydrolytic enzymes chitinase and β -1,3-glucanase

(Jach et al 1995, Zhu et al 1994). We isolated a *M. grisea*-induced promoter that was later used to drive antifungal genes in rice to suppress the effects of fungal infection.

Rice cDNAs, whose genes exhibited elevated expression during rice blast infection, have been isolated through differential screening (Talbot et al 1993). One of these cDNAs, MAG-7, was chosen as a source of the *M. grisea*-induced promoter. MAG-7 was found to share homology with a known class of PR proteins (PR-10 proteins) found in various plants (van Loon et al 1994).

Southern blot hybridization of rice genomic DNA (varieties Co 39, IR36, and IR54) probed with the MAG-7 cDNA indicated that these varieties contain multiple (2-5) copies of the MAG-7 gene

1. Northern blot analyses comparing the presence of different rice mRNA transcripts at various times following *Magnaporthe grisea* infection. 10- μ g samples of total RNA isolated either from uninfected 3-wk-old Co 39 seedlings (0 h) or from 3-wk-old seedlings infected for 12, 18, 24, 36, 48, 72, or 144 h were hybridized to different rice PR-10 probes. (a) Total RNA hybridized with a 814-bp nonspecific probe from a PR-10a cDNA, which shares homology with all three rice PR-10 genes. (b) Total RNA hybridized to a 198-bp probe derived from the 5' untranslated region of the PR-10a gene. (c) Total RNA hybridized to a 230-bp probe derived from the 3' untranslated region of the PR-10b gene. (d) Total RNA hybridized to a 231-bp probe derived from the 5' untranslated region of the PR-10c gene. The intensity of chloroplast 23S rRNA in b, c, and d shows similar amounts of RNA loaded onto gels.